

CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF ESSENTIAL OIL *LAGOCHILUS SETULOSUS*

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ABSTRACT. The study of volatile components by the method of gas chromatography-mass spectral analysis of the composition of essential oils obtained by steam distillation from the aerial part of *Lagochilus setulosus* collected during the period of mass flowering in the Tashkent region of the Republic of Uzbekistan. As a result of the studies carried out, 67 compounds were identified in the composition of essential oils obtained by steam distillation methods, respectively. The dominant components are Valensin (1.019%), Terpineol (1.095%), Episonarene (1.130%), α -iso-Terpinolen (1.220%), α -Amorphine (2.147%), β -Fellandren (14.312%).

Keywords: qualitative analysis, chromatography-mass spectrometry, component composition, monoterpenoids, fatty acids, hydrocarbons.

Introduction. The genus *Lagochilus* is the most widely represented in the Lamiaceae family. More than 16 of its species grow on the territory of Uzbekistan. Representatives of the genus – *L. setulosus* are perennial, stems at the base are woody, thin, straight, glabrous or bristly, later white, shiny, 30-80 cm tall. The leaves are rhombic, broadly ovate, deeply dissected or separated, the blades are short-pointed, but devoid of acuity, glabrous on long, narrowly winged petioles in the middle and upper leaves are shorter. The flowers are sessile, 4-6 in the axils of the upper leaves. Bracts-spines are thin, needle-shaped. The calyx is narrow-ringed with narrowly triangular, prickly teeth. The corolla is white with brown spots, 2.3-3 cm

long. Flowering in May-September [1]. Different groups of biologically active substances have been found in hares.

The aerial parts of *L. setulosus* contain triterpenoids, alkaloids, tannins, vitamins, flavonoids, carbohydrates, organic acids [2,3,4]. In folk medicine, *L. setulosus* is used as an expectorant, anti-inflammatory, tonic, antispasmodic, hemostatic and sedative. The infusion in the experiment causes an increase in heart rate [5]. To date, the chemical composition of the essential oil of the species *L.setulosus* has not been studied. This paper presents the results of chemical analysis of essential oils from the aboveground parts of *L.setulosus* obtained by chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS).

Research methodology. To do this, 50 g of aboveground parts of *L. setulosus* were placed in a working flask with a capacity of 500 ml, and filled with distilled water (about 200 ml). The distillate was distilled for 2 hours using the Clevenger apparatus. The resulting distillate was extracted with dichloromethane, the extract of essential oils was dried with anhydrous sodium sulfate. The resulting oil (yield about 0.6%) was stored in the refrigerator at -4 °C before use.

The essential oil components were analyzed by chromatography-mass spectrometry on an Agilent 7890B gas chromatograph with a 5977A quadrupole mass spectrometer as a detector and an automatic input system. We used a 30 m quartz column VF-Wax ms (100% polyethylene glycol) with an inner diameter of 0.25 microns (Agilent Technologies, Netherlands), a carrier gas - helium with a constant flow of 0.9 ml/min. Evaporator temperature: 280 °C. Ion source temperature: 230 °C. Interface temperature between GC and MS detector: 280 °C. Ionization of molecules was carried out by electrons (70 eV). Data collection was carried out in the area of 45-950 a.m. A solution of essential oil in dichloromethane (0.5 µl) with a flow separation of 1:20 was automatically introduced into the evaporator. The column temperature was maintained at 50 °C for 5 minutes, then raised from 50 to 280 °C with an interval of 5 °C per minute, and at the end the column was kept at 280 °C for 15 minutes; injector temperature 250 °C; detector

temperature 270 °C. Enhanced ChemStation software, MSD version F.01.01.2317 (Agilent Technologies) was used to record and integrate chromatograms. The quantitative content of essential oil components was calculated from the areas of chromatographic peaks.

The qualitative analysis was based on a comparison of retention indices (RI) and total mass spectra with the corresponding data of components of reference oils and pure compounds with data from the chromatography-mass spectrometric data library and data from the Wiley Registry of Mass Spectral Data library (9th ed.), NIST Mass Spectral Library (2011), and also catalogues [6,7]. The composition of *L. setulosus* essential oils is presented in Table 1. As a result of the study, the presence of 67 components in the composition of the essential oil was revealed. The total content of the identified components was 90.4%.

Research results. As a result of the study, 67 compounds were identified and their composition was established. (Table 1). Among the identified compounds in the essential oil of the aboveground parts of *L. setulosus*, terpenoid compounds predominate (mg per 1000 g of dry leaves) – 1047; fatty acids – 258.04; hydrocarbons – 129.73; an insignificant amount of aromatic compounds – 29.74 was found.

Table 1.

The composition of the identified substances of the essential oil of the aboveground parts of *Lagochilus setulosus*.

No	Retention index	Name of compounds	Contents of components
1	884	Santen	0,037
2	921	Tricyclene	0,171
3	926	3-Thujone	0,038
4	932	α -Pinen	54,572
5	947	Camphene	1,000

6	952	Verbenene	0,028
7	973	Sabinene	0,017
8	975	β -Pinene	3,199
9	991	β -Myrsene	0,811
10	1004	α -Phellandrene	0,424
11	1010	Δ^3 -Carene	0,323
12	1017	α -Terpinene	0,195
13	1022	<i>m</i> -Cymen	0,052
14	1028	β -Phellandrene	14,312
15	1038	<i>c</i> - β -Ocimen	0,027
16	1058	γ -Terpinene	0,143
17	1070	<i>p</i> -Mentha-3,8-diene	0,028
18	1086	<i>iso</i> -Terpinolene	1,220
19	1103	Photocitral	0,015
20	1113	α -Fenchol	0,069
21	1120	Dehidro-sabinaketone	0,029
22	1126	α -Campholenal	0,023
23	1140	<i>c</i> -Sabinol	0,042
24	1150	<i>neo-iso</i> -Thujol	0,033
25	1158	Decane-2-one	0,098
26	1166	Borneol	0,133
27	1177	Terpinen-4-ol	0,170
28	1187	Crypton	0,033
29	1191	α -Terpineol	1,095
30	1199	Methyl chavicol	0,214
31	1215	Dehydro- <i>iso</i> -carveol	0,214
32	1221	α -Phenyl acetate	0,015
33	1229	Citronellol	0,056

34	1236	Tymol methyl ester	0,399
35	1255	Piperitone	0,025
36	1273	Decanol	0,019
37	1277	Isopulegol acetate	0,043
38	1280	Mentha-1,3-dien-7-ol	0,052
39	1287	Bornyl acetate	0,788
40	1294	Undecan-2-one	0,043
41	1335	α -Cadinene	0,029
42	1338	Δ -Elemene	0,020
43	1344	Sylvine-1-ene	0,067
44	1351	α -Terpineol acetate	0,320
45	1351	α -Cubebene	0,089
46	1352	α -Longipinene	0,171
47	1372	α -Ylangene	0,074
48	1378	α -Copaene	0,221
49	1387	Bourbonene	0,029
50	1401	β -Longipinene	0,036
51	1408	Longifolene	0,093
52	1422	Caryophyllene	0,499
53	1432	β -Copaene	0,197
54	1433	β -Gurjunene	0,041
55	1440	Aromadendrene	0,265
56	1448	<i>sol</i> -Muurool-3,5,-diene	0,077
57	1452	Selina-5,11-diene	0,206
58	1456	Humulen	0,210
59	1471	Carota-5,8-diene	0,071
60	1471	β -Neoclovene	0,220
61	1479	γ -Himachalene	0,042

62	1480	γ -Muurolene	0,360
63	1482	α -Amorphene	2,147
64	1490	Alloaromadendr-9-ene	0,263
65	1494	Valencene	1,019
66	1496	α -Selinene	0,120
67	1500	Epizonarene	1,130

Conclusions. The component composition of the essential oil of the leaves of the aerial parts of *L.setulosus* was determined for the first time by chromatography-mass spectrometry. 67 compounds have been detected and their composition has been established. Among the identified compounds in the essential oil of the leaves of *L.setulosus*, terpenoid compounds predominate (mg per 1000 g of dry leaves) – 1047; fatty acids – 258.04; hydrocarbons – 129.73; an insignificant amount of aromatic compounds – 29.74 was found.

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